
Is Solar Power a Cost-Effective Energy Alternative to Traditional Energy? A Benefit-Cost Analysis on Taylor County Solar Facility in Georgia

INTRODUCTION

With the announcement of the Clean Power Plan in August 2015, the United States made a commitment to tackle climate change for the sake of both current and future generations. This action establishes a foundation on which the state of Georgia can strengthen its renewable energy portfolio; this portfolio represented only 6 percent of Georgia States' electricity generation in 2014 (EIA 2015a).

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Southern Power Company's proposed 911-acre, 146 megawatt (MW) solar farm, purchased in December 2014, will meet the energy needs of 21,000 homes (Southern Company 2014). The solar farm is located around the outskirts of the Fall Line Sandhill Wildlife Management Area (WMA) in Taylor County, Georgia and construction began in September 2015. The Georgia State Department of Natural Resources purchased the WMA in 2006 to preserve a wide range of endangered species and plants; previously, the property was private timberlands. 876 acres in the WMA are currently protected, sheltering endangered native species such as Bachman's sparrows, gopher tortoises, southern hognose snakes, and gopher frogs (Jensen, n.d). The WMA also provides recreational activities such as hunting, hiking, and picnicking for local residents. Ecologists are concerned about the detrimental impacts to the endangered species from the installation of the 1.6 million solar photovoltaic panels.

This analysis focuses on measuring the benefits and costs of this 911-acre solar farm and evaluating the net impact to examine whether the predicted negative impact on wildlife populations outweighs the advantages of constructing a solar power plant in Georgia. Additional analysis will incorporate a comparison with traditional energy sources – natural gas and coal.

STANDING, SOCIAL DISCOUNT RATE, AND OTHER ASSUMPTIONS

We grant standing to the Georgia State taxpayers. Benefits and costs accrued in this analysis are associated with the Southern Power Company and Georgia State residents. Utilizing existing benefit-cost analyses on solar power and other renewable energies, we consider a six percent social discount rate (SDR) for the initial analysis (Oxera 2011) but incorporate three and nine percent rates in the final sensitivity analysis (USFS 2011, Wampler 2011).

This analysis is based on the project’s 25-year timeframe (Southern Company 2015). We assume all the capital and upfront costs happen in the initial year (Year 0), at the end of 2015, whereas annual benefits and costs are accrued at the end of each year from 2016 (Year 1) to 2040 (Year 25). The project is estimated to meet the energy needs of 21,000 households. Utilizing an annual energy consumption average of 14,500 kilowatt-hours (kWh) per household in Georgia, we estimate the yearly energy output of the solar farm to be 304,500,000 kWh (EIA 2009).

Due to the difficulty and complexity of calculating the social welfare increase associated with this solar facility, we are not able to include this impact into the benefits. Instead, we equate the benefits of the solar farm with the opportunity cost of not constructing a traditional energy facility in its place. Georgia State relies on coal and natural gas for its electricity generation; they account for 36 percent and 32 percent, respectively, of Georgia’s energy production (EIA 2015a). Therefore, the costs associated with an alternative coal or a natural gas facility will serve as our counterfactuals. We assume both alternative projects will have the same electricity generation capacity of the solar farm: 146,000 kW or approximately 304,500,000 kWh.

IMPACT CATEGORIES

Impacts of this solar facility include the capital, operation and maintenance (O&M) costs of the facility, environmental costs, and people’s willingness to pay (WTP) for renewable energy. Table 1 explains the impact categories in detail.

TABLE 1: IMPACT CATEGORIES OF TAYLOR COUNTY SOLAR FACILITY

Impact Categories	Description
<i>%HQHÀWV</i>	
Opportunity cost of alternative facilities	Costs include capital and O&M costs, cost of carbon and methane emissions, cost of fuel (coal and natural gas), and cost of pollutants.

WTP for renewable energy	How much people value using renewable energy, over nonrenewable energy, on average (Note: WTP for renewable energy is included in the opportunity costs of the alternative coal or natural gas facilities.).
Costs	
<i>Construction and O&M costs</i>	
Capital cost	One-time construction cost of the solar facility that occurs in Year 0.
Operation and maintenance cost	Operation and maintenance cost that occurs each year from Year 1 to Year 25.
<i>Environmental costs</i>	
Lost carbon sequestration	Loss of carbon sequestered by previous timberlands covered on the solar facility tracts. Accrued every year from Year 0 to Year 25.
Carbon emissions	Solar panels emit carbon but at a lower rate than conventional energy.
Wildlife impact	Estimate loss of wildlife population due to the solar facility. We use WTP to monetize the value of wildlife.
Lost ecosystem services	Lost ecosystem services from the removal of previous timberlands to construct the solar project as well as the impact of the solar facility on the WMA. Accrued annually from Year 0 to Year 25.

BENEFITS: OPPORTUNITY COST OF COAL & NATURAL GAS

As mentioned above, we consider the opportunity cost of *not* building a coal or natural gas facility as the benefits to this solar project. We divide the opportunity costs into the following six categories:

i. Capital and Operation & Maintenance Costs

The Open Energy Information (n.d.) site provides information on predicted and historical costs of capital and operation for a range of energy sources, including solar, natural gas, and coal. Both capital and fixed operating costs incorporate the estimated kW production whereas variable operating costs use the estimated mWh production. Capital costs of an equivalent natural gas facility are \$201,480,000 and the annual operating costs (fixed and variable) are \$3,200,980. Capital costs for a comparable coal plant are \$554,800,000, and the annual operating costs are \$10,718,180. O&M costs include the price of fuel (coal or natural gas) to generate

the electricity, but not the associated transportation costs. (See VIII. Limitations for a detailed explanation.) **ii. Social Cost of Carbon**

The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, n.d.) has conducted numerous studies focused on quantifying the external cost of carbon dioxide. In their calculations, the EPA (n.d.) uses estimated costs of an additional metric ton of carbon emitted into the atmosphere on “net agricultural productivity, human health, property damages from increased flood risk, and changes in energy system costs, such as reduced costs for heating and increased costs for air conditioning” (p. 2). Using a discount rate of three percent, the EPA estimates a cost of approximately \$40 for each metric ton of carbon (2015\$). According to the EIA (n.d.), coal emits approximately 2.15 pounds of carbon dioxide for every kWh produced (equivalent to a little less than 300,00 metric tons); the annual carbon cost for coal is therefore about \$11,877,921.83. Natural gas is estimated to emit 1.21 pounds of carbon dioxide for every kWh (equivalent to a little less than 200,000 metric tons), culminating in a total carbon cost of \$6,684,800 (EIA n.d.).

iii. Opportunity Cost of Coal & Natural Gas Facility

The US Energy Information Administration provided information on how much coal and natural gas is needed to generate 1kWh of electricity (n.d.), as well as the average coal and natural gas prices (EIA 2015b; EIA 2015c). The generation of 1kWh of electricity requires 0.05 pounds of coal or 10.1 cubic feet of natural gas. We use the average natural gas and coal prices from 2010 to 2014 to calculate the cost of fuel as well as the standard deviations for the sensitivity analysis. The annual cost of coal and natural gas is \$ 17,023,133.4 and \$ 34,475,044.39, respectively, from Year 1 to Year 25. **iv. Pollutant Cost**

Utilizing a study conducted by Harvard Medical School’s Center for Health and the Global Environments, we value additional environmental, non-climate pollutant costs for coal at \$0.178/kWh and natural gas at 0.0016/kWh (Energy & Policy Institute, n.d.). Using the project’s output of 304,500,000 kWh, we estimate the annual pollutant cost of coal at \$9,744,000 and natural gas at \$487,200.

v. Social Cost of Methane

The National Center for Environmental Economics monetized the estimated cost of an additional metric ton of methane into the atmosphere, focusing on specific disadvantages to “agriculture, energy production, water availability, human health, coastal communities, [and] biodiversity” (Martin & Newbold 2012, p. 958). Using a three percent discount rate, the group estimated the total cost of an additional metric ton of methane into the atmosphere at \$810 (Martin & Newbold 2012).

The Energy Information Administration (n.d.) states that a kilowatt-hour from natural gas requires approximately 10.1 cubic feet of natural gas. Multiplied by the total kWh produced by the solar farm (304,500,000), a natural gas plant requires

3,075,450,000 cubic feet of natural gas to provide the equivalent amount of electricity. Converting this number to methane emissions requires an understanding of the percentage of natural gas lost during production, which the EPA estimates at about two percent. If two percent of the natural gas is lost, then the natural gas plant would need to extract 3,136,959,000 ($3,075,450,000 \times 1.02$) cubic feet of natural gas to generate the specific kWh. The two percent of natural gas lost is equivalent to 62,739,180 cubic feet, of which 80 percent is methane. 50,191,344 cubic feet of methane is equivalent to approximately 1,030 metric tons. Using the social cost of methane detailed above (\$810/metric ton), we arrive at an annual methane cost of \$834,804 or \$5.71 for every kW of electricity produced.

vi. Willingness to Pay for Renewable Energy

People intrinsically value clean energy; this valuation method is referred to as the “warm-glow” effect. We take this effect into consideration by looking into contingent valuation studies on people’s willingness to pay for renewable energy. This category of benefit is then included into the opportunity cost of a coal or natural gas facility. Soon and Ahmad (2015) summarized worldwide studies on WTP for renewable energy.

We extracted three different contingent valuations and converted the results into 2015 values using an online inflation calculation tool (US Inflation Calculator n.d.). Aldy, Kotchen and Leiserowitz (2012) found that a US household is willing to pay \$171 every year for using renewable energy. That estimate provides an annual WTP for renewable energy of \$3,597,090 (mean). Borchers, Duke and Parsons (2007) estimate WTP at \$269 per household per year, which is totaled at \$5,657,610 every year (high). A low total value of \$2,935,170 is derived from a Whithead and Cherry (2007) study in which a household valued renewable energy at \$139 per year. Low and high values are not considered in the benefit-cost calculation but are utilized in the Monte Carlo simulations for the sensitivity analysis.

COSTS: SOLAR ENERGY

i. Capital and Operating & Maintenance Costs

Southern Power reports that the solar farm in Taylor County, Georgia will produce 146,000 kW and about 304,500 mWh (Southern Company 2014). Using this information, we estimate the capital costs of the solar farm at \$538,740,00 and the annual operating costs (fixed) at \$2,336,000 (OEI, n.d.). Utilizing discount rates of three, six, and nine percent for annual operating costs (Years 1 through 25), we compare the capital and O&M costs for solar to natural gas and coal in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 CAPITAL AND O&M COSTS PER ENERGY SOURCE

Although solar energy has a very low annual cost, it has a higher capital cost when compared to natural gas; the capital costs of solar energy are 2.7 times higher than those of natural gas for the equivalent kWh production. On the other hand, solar energy does have the lowest annual costs excluding costs of capital. In the following sections, we investigate additional costs related to producing energy via solar facilities.

ii. Social Cost of Carbon

Although solar panels are presented as the green alternative to traditional fuels, they still emit carbon dioxide. EDF Energy (2011) reports that the carbon footprint of a solar panel is roughly 72 grams per kWh. The annual carbon cost for the solar farm is therefore about \$876,960, which is equivalent to 7.4 percent of the annual carbon footprint of coal and 13.2 percent of the annual carbon footprint of natural gas.

iii. Environmental Costs

We identified three environmental costs associated with building the solar facility that will occur annually from Year 0 to Year 25: 1) carbon sequestration loss, 2) wildlife conservation (on the solar facility site and the WMA), and 3) ecosystem

services (both for the facility site and WMA). Table 2 details the ranges of each cost that occur in Year 0 or, the initial environmental costs. Table 3 lists the ranges of annual costs (including the cost of carbon emissions from the previous section) that occur between Years 1 to 25.

The 911-acre solar facility incurs costs from lost carbon sequestration (due to tree removal), ecosystem services, and wildlife populations. A 2012 Ecosystem Services Report estimates the annual value per acre of carbon sequestration to be \$1,280 (all values here are in 2015\$), ecosystem services (recreation, aesthetics, wildlife habitat, and natural resource conservation) to be \$5,210.61, and wildlife populations to be \$130.89 (Escobedo & Timilsina 2012). To find the total costs of the solar farm, we multiplied these values by the number of acres (911). We based the impact to wildlife species populations on a WTP study for “avoided population reductions” of five “charismatic species”; this value is a conservative estimate of the total amount of species that will be affected by the project.

TABLE 2 INITIAL ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS OF SOLAR FACILITY

SOLAR FACILITY: Environmental Costs			
Year 0 Costs (2015 USD)	MINIMUM	MEAN	MAXIMUM
Carbon sequestration loss (trees)	\$ 516,710.09	,271,874.43\$ 1	,572,683.38\$ 10
Lost Wildlife conservation (solar facility)	\$ 119,240.79	\$ 119,240.79	\$ 119,240.79
Lost ecosystem services (solar facility)	,746,865.71\$ 4	,746,865.71\$ 4	,746,865.71\$ 4
Lost Wildlife Conservation (WMA)	,732.98\$ 5	,664.91\$ 28	,329.82\$ 57
Lost ecosystem services (WMA)	\$ 228,224.72	,141,123.59\$ 1	,282,247.18\$ 2
Total Initial Environmental Costs	,616,774.29\$ 5	,307,769.43\$ 7	,778,366.88\$ 17

Calculating the impacts of the solar facility surrounding the WMA was more difficult and required a meta-analysis combining the WTP results from the Florida study and a 2011 report that discussed impacts to wildlife populations (Escobedo & Timilsina 2012; Lieberman, Lyons, & Tucker 2011). Using the two publications, we established a range of potential wildlife population reductions from five to 50 percent with an average of 25 percent. We used five, 25, and 50 percent population reductions to estimate the “percentage or area of impact” and generate the minimum, mean, and maximum costs. Next, we calculated the total effect of the solar site on the WMAs wildlife by multiplying the *total WMA acreage* (876 acres) by the *percentage of impact* and multiplying that value by the *WTP for avoided reduction* per acre.

TABLE 3 ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS OF SOLAR FACILITY

SOLAR FACILITY: Environmental Costs			
Year 1- 25 Costs (2015 USD)	MINIMUM	MEAN	MAXIMUM
Carbon sequestration loss (solar facility)	\$ 516,710.09	,271,874.43\$ 1	,572,683.38\$ 10
Cost of Carbon (Panels)	\$ 876,960.00	\$ 876,960.00	\$ 876,960.00
Lost ecosystem services (solar facility)	,746,865.71\$ 4	,746,865.71\$ 4	\$ 4 ,746,865.71
Lost Wildlife conservation (solar facility)	\$ 119,240.79	\$ 119,240.79	\$ 119,240.79
Lost Wildlife Conservation (WMA)	,732.98\$ 5	,664.91\$ 28	,329.82\$ 57
Lost ecosystem services (WMA)	\$ 228,224.72	,141,123.59\$ 1	,282,247.18\$ 2
Total Annual Environmental Costs	,493,734.29\$ 6	,184,729.43\$ 8	,655,326.88\$ 18

Because changes in wildlife populations are linked to changes in habitat, we used the same percentages (five, 25, & 50 percent impact to WMA) to calculate a range of costs attributed to lost ecosystem services in the WMA. This function is similar to the one above: *total WMA acreage* (876 acres) by the *percentage of impact* and by the *WTP for ecosystem services* per acre.

Carbon emission costs of the solar panels are calculated at a rate of 72 grams of CO₂ per kWh, with an annual production of 304,500,000 kWh, and an expected cost of \$40 per metric ton (EDF Energy 2011; EPA n.d.). The total environmental costs, both on the facility site and on the WMA, compose a very small percentage of the project’s net present value (NPV) (see Figure 2).

FIGURE 2 PERCENTAGE OF PROJECT COSTS ATTRIBUTED TO ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS

Percentage of Annual costs attributed to WMA (not discounted)	11.23%
Percentage of NPV attributed to WMA (compared to coal)	2.39%
Percentage of NPV attributed to WMA (compared to natural gas)	10.68%

COMPARISON

As illustrated in Figure 3 below, there is considerable cost variability among the three energy sources. Solar may have the lowest carbon and pollutant costs of the three sources surveyed, but has a surprisingly high capital cost when compared to natural gas; 2.67 times more up-front capital is needed for a solar farm than a natural gas plant. On the other hand, solar has the lowest cumulative operation and

maintenance costs when compared to natural gas or coal. A major benefit of solar is its dependence on solar energy, eliminating the need for a non-renewable source to provide energy.

FIGURE 3 SUMMARY OF NPV COSTS BY PROJECT TYPE

(Note: Does not include WTP for Renewable Energy as that was included as a Benefit for Solar)

Putting aside capital costs, the total yearly costs for the three sources are:

xSolar Panels: \$47,371,429.03 or \$0.16 per kWh x

Coal: \$836,066,264.06 or \$2.75 per kWh x

Natural Gas: \$352,270,378.39 or \$1.16 per kWh

The largest benefit for installing solar panels is the reduction of carbon and particulate emissions into the atmosphere. Despite these benefits, a solar farm is a large financial investment and requires significant upfront capital. If an energy organization did not consider the long-term benefits of solar, it may choose a more affordable short-term alternative such as a natural gas facility.

BENEFIT-COST CALCULATIONS

Based on the aforementioned assumptions and the monetization process of all impact categories, we calculated the baseline scenario with a six percent social discount rate within a 25-year timeframe.

NPV of Costs and Benefits (Mean values)				0.06 NPV (6%)	
Year	Benefits Coal Alt.	Benefits Natural Gas Alt.	Costs	NPV Coal Alternative	NPV Natural Gas Alternati
0	\$ 554,800,000.00	\$ 201,480,000.0000	\$ (546,047,769.43)	,752,230.57\$ 8	\$ (344,567,769.4300)
1	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	\$ 49,229,835.66	,565,273.3583\$ 36
2	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,443,241.19\$ 46	,495,540.9041\$ 34
3	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,814,378.48\$ 43	,542,963.1171\$ 32
4	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,334,319.32\$ 41	,700,908.6010\$ 30
5	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,994,640.87\$ 38	,963,121.3217\$ 28
6	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	\$ 36,787,397.05	,323,699.3601\$ 27
7	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,705,091.56\$ 34	,777,074.8680\$ 25
8	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,740,652.41\$ 32	,317,995.1585\$ 24
9	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,887,407.93\$ 30	,941,504.8665\$ 22
10	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,139,064.09\$ 29	,642,929.1194\$ 21
11	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,489,683.10\$ 27	,417,857.6598\$ 20
12	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,933,663.30\$ 25	,262,129.8677\$ 19
13	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,465,720.10\$ 24	,171,820.6299\$ 18
14	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,080,868.02\$ 23	,143,227.0094\$ 17
15	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	\$ 21,774,403.79	,172,855.6692\$ 16
16	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,541,890.37\$ 20	,257,411.0087\$ 15
17	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,379,141.86\$ 19	,393,783.9705\$ 14
18	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,282,209.30\$ 18	,579,041.4816\$ 13
19	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,247,367.26\$ 17	,810,416.4920\$ 12
20	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,271,101.19\$ 16	,085,298.5774\$ 12
21	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,350,095.46\$ 15	,401,225.0730\$ 11

22	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,481,222.14\$ 14	,755,872.7104\$ 10
23	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,661,530.32\$ 13	,147,049.7268\$ 10
24	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,888,236.15\$ 12	,572,688.4215\$ 9
25	,704,355.23\$ 62	,279,919.19\$ 49	\$ (10,520,729.43)	,158,713.35\$ 12	,030,838.1335\$ 9
				\$ 675,834,104.85	\$ 150,904,757.68

The net present value is positive with both alternatives utilizing a six percent SDR. **The benefits of the Taylor County Solar Facility outweigh its costs.**

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

To capture the variation in costs and benefits of the energy sources, we conducted two forms of sensitivity analysis: Monte Carlo simulations and differing social discount rates. The Monte Carlo simulations were used to determine the probable mean NPV of the two base case project alternatives. The simulations also generated the probabilities of the substitute scenarios “breaking-even”, or reaching a NPV of \$0 or less, to determine the risks of the project. The different social discount rates are reflective of the uncertainty in the ecological components of the benefit-cost analysis or the solar energy market.

i. Monte Carlo: Assumptions

To conduct the Monte Carlo analysis, we operated under four key assumptions:

1. Each variable (cost or benefit) is normally distributed.
2. The values used in the NPV calculations are representative of the solar project being completed in Taylor County, Georgia.
3. The social discount rate is held constant at 6 percent.
4. Reported variables without standard deviations or data ranges are held constant.

The distributions of each cost and benefit variable are assumed to be normal because research did not reveal either “theoretical or empirical evidence” of another appropriate distribution (Boardman, Greenberg, Vining, & Weimer 2011, p. 184). While conducting research, we selected reports and literature based on their credibility, proximity or direct relation to the energy and environmental markets in Georgia, and if the data was the most recent available. Despite this, it was not possible to use perfect information for every value. To continue with the analysis, we therefore assume the values used in the scenarios are representative of the true costs and benefits of the solar project.

We held the SDR constant for the Monte Carlo simulations at six percent, the median value of the three social discount rates used in the second of the sensitivity analyses. The SDR is not an active variable in the Monte Carlo component because it is isolated and studied separately. Several variables (e.g. carbon costs of solar panels) were published without a standard deviation or range of values. This made it difficult to estimate the variation and uncertainty to include in the probability distribution. Lacking this information, we held these variables constant rather than allow them to fluctuate in an inaccurate or unrepresentative manner.

ii. Monte Carlo: Results

When comparing the proposed solar facility to the opportunity costs of coal, the probable mean NPV is about \$670 million (see Figure 4). The probability of the solar facility generating a positive NPV, or “breaking-even”, is 0.9632. Conversely, there is a 3.68 percent chance that within the 25-year timeframe the coal alternative is more beneficial than a solar plant. Compared to coal, the solar project has a 68 percent chance that the NPV of the project will fall between \$283 million and \$1.058 billion. For a public decision maker in Georgia, such as the Georgia Department of Natural Resources, these results indicate a solar facility will provide a net social benefit even though it is located next to the Fall Line Sandhill WMA. In this case, the project provides a net benefit to society.

If this same analysis is conducted using the opportunity costs of a natural gas site, we find a mean NPV of approximately \$140 million (see Figure 5). Based on the simulation’s probability distribution, the NPV of the solar project compared to natural gas falls between -\$81 million and \$361 million in 68 percent of the trials conducted. The range of one standard deviation away from the mean encompassing negative and positive values is an indication of uncertainty in the costs and benefits of a solar facility with respect to natural gas.

FIGURE 5 NPV OF SOLAR COMPARED TO NATURAL GAS

FIGURE 5 NPV OF SOLAR COMPARED TO NATURAL GAS

When comparing solar costs to the natural gas alternative, the facility has a 74.19 percent chance that the solar project will provide more benefits than natural gas. However, the probability of the solar facility not “breaking-even” after 25 years is 0.2581. The probability the facility will not break-even is higher than that of the coal alternative. This probability reflects the variation and uncertainty in the costs of natural gas, making it a comparatively riskier project alternative. From a decision maker’s perspective, the results still indicate a solar plant will provide positive social benefits and should be undertaken.

iii. Social Discount Rates: Assumptions

We utilize three social discount rates (three, six, and nine percent) to analyze the sensitivity of the project's NPV to discounted future costs and benefits. The minimum SDR of three percent was selected because it is the value used in cost-benefit analyses by the United States Forest Service (USFS 2011) and represents the ecological and environmental components of discounting future costs and benefits. The median and maximum rates, six and nine percent (Wampler 2011; Oxera 2011), are rates used to assess solar and green energy projects and reflect the impact of discounting on energy market rates. Using a variety of discount rates informs decision makers of possible impacts to the solar facility's expected NPV as a result of changing conditions.

iv. Social Discount Rates: Results

As shown in Table 5 below, the NPV of the solar facility is always positive across the three discount rates when compared to both the coal and natural gas opportunity costs. **Within a 25-year timeline, the benefits associated with constructing a solar facility next to the WMA will outweigh the costs compared to natural gas or coal at each discount rate evaluated.** In that same timeframe, the benefits of the solar facility will be less than the opportunity costs of the natural gas alternative if the SDR is 10 percent or higher. While this Internal Rate of Return (IRR) does represent some sensitivity to selecting the appropriate discount rate, it is higher than the highest rate used in the solar energy market and may not reflect an accurate value for assessing this project.

TABLE 5 SDR SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF NPV FOR PROJECT ALTERNATIVES

Discount Rate	NPV - Solar vs Coal	NPV - Solar vs Natural Gas
3%	\$917,433,413.76	\$330,351,726.25
6%	\$675,834,104.85	\$150,904,757.68
9%	\$521,330,049.10	\$36,147,457.41
IRR	*	10%

* The NPV of solar compared to coal is positive for every discount rate and therefore does not have an Internal Rate of Return where the project breaks-even.

LIMITATIONS

Our results contain several important limitations. A primary limitation that affected several aspects of our research was the lack of a published Environmental Impact Assessment or Statement for the solar farm (EIA and EIS, respectively). Without these documents, we were unable to determine the most likely alternative use of

the solar project's 911 acres or the expected environmental impacts to the adjacent WMA. We addressed this lack of information by researching ecological effects from similar projects and assuming that most likely alternatives would follow trends in Georgia's current energy portfolio. In the case that these assumptions are incorrect, it will be necessary to reassess the social costs and benefits of the solar facility in light of the new data.

A further challenge to our analysis is the difficulty in quantifying the change in consumer and producer surplus for the construction of the solar farm near the WMA. We approximate these changes by incorporating the opportunity costs of possible substitute energy facilities (Boardman, Greenberg, Vining, & Weimer 2011). Again, this factor is dependent upon our assumption that alternative energy sources would reflect Georgia's current energy portfolio. This will change if decision makers identify another alternative or base case scenario.

Another limitation to this benefit-cost analysis is the lack of complete value ranges or standard deviations from key reports and literature sources. This restricted the variables that we were able to incorporate into the Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis. In an effort to overcome this, we conducted meta-analyses for the WTP for wildlife conservation, "warm glow" associated with green energy, and ecosystem services. For these values, there may be external validity issues if the range in the estimated WTP is not applicable or relevant to the distribution of the true values.

The final aspect that influences the benefit-cost analysis is the difficulty in estimating the transportation costs of coal and natural gas. We omitted these costs because of the difficulty in identifying the origins of the materials and direct transportation route. The calculated NPVs may be lower than the true values because of this omission.

CONCLUSION

The net present values for solar energy compared to coal and natural gas are always positive when using three, six and nine percent social discount rates within a 25year timeframe. As this solar project is already under construction and will go into operation next year, **we recommend continued construction and operation.** However, the result is still conservative due to the above limitations. Future analysis, with if possible the integration of more socio-behavioural constructs, like leverage points (Meadows, 1999) or social tipping dynamics (Berger, 2021; Milkoreit, 2023; Campfens et al., 2025) would give additional insights into the societal developments underlying profitability of Solar BCA.

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